

THE TEACHING OF READING IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE APPROACHES: BELIEFS AND EXPERIENCES OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

LOS ENFOQUES DE LA ENSEÑANZA DE LA LECTURA EN LENGUA INGLESA:
CREENCIAS Y EXPERIENCIAS DE ESTUDIANTES DE ESCUELA PRIMARIA

O ENSINO DE LEITURA NAS ABORDAGENS DE LÍNGUA INGLESA: CRENÇAS E
EXPERIÊNCIAS DE ALUNOS DO ENSINO FUNDAMENTAL

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Abstract

The central discussion of this research is studies aimed at the beliefs and experiences of elementary school students about teaching reading in English language (EL). The EL teaching and learning process is conditioned by a series of factors, among which we can highlight the practice of reading. The practice of reading, in a way, consists of the process of looking at a series of written symbols and constructing meanings, allowing those words to construct meanings in our (un)conscious. The authors who make up our theoretical assumptions are: Barcelos (2004), Vieira-Abrahão (2006), Oliveira (2007), Paiva (2008), Miccoli (2010), Masetto (2012), Oliveira (2013), Rojo (2013), Freire (2003), Solé (2014), among others. This study is characterized as an investigation within the limits of applied linguistics, of a descriptive and interpretive nature. The subjects of this study are two elementary school students from a public school. To collect the corpus, we used a 'self-report' as a research instrument. The results achieved in this investigation show the improvement and recognition of reading as a fundamental point in the EL classroom. The students' testimonies show a satisfactory reality in the EL teaching process, especially with regard to reading practice. Teaching reading in EL can be an alternative approach for the public school context.

Keywords: Reading; Language Teaching; Beliefs; Experiences.

Resumen

La discusión central de esta investigación son los estudios dirigidos a las creencias y experiencias de estudiantes de educación primaria respecto a la enseñanza de la lectura en inglés (EL). El proceso de enseñanza-aprendizaje de la EL está condicionado por una serie de

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factores, entre los que podemos destacar la práctica de la lectura. La práctica de la lectura, en cierto modo, consiste en el proceso de mirar una serie de símbolos escritos y construir significados, permitiendo que esas palabras construyan significados en nuestro (in)consciente. El objetivo general es investigar las creencias y experiencias de estudiantes de educación primaria sobre la enseñanza de la lectura en EL. Los autores que conforman nuestros supuestos teóricos son: Barcelos (2004), Vieira-Abrahão (2006), Oliveira (2007), Paiva (2008), Miccoli (2010), Masetto (2012), Oliveira (2013), Rojo (2013). Freire (2003), Solé (2014), entre otros. Este estudio se caracteriza como una investigación dentro de los límites de la lingüística aplicada, de carácter descriptivo e interpretativo. Los sujetos de este estudio son dos estudiantes de educación primaria de una escuela pública. Para recopilar el corpus utilizamos el “autoinforme” como instrumento de investigación. Los resultados alcanzados en esta investigación muestran la mejora y reconocimiento de la lectura como punto fundamental en el aula de AL. Los testimonios de los estudiantes muestran una realidad satisfactoria respecto del proceso de enseñanza de la AL, especialmente en lo que respecta a la práctica lectora. La enseñanza de la lectura en LI puede ser un enfoque alternativo para el contexto de la escuela pública.

Palabras clave: Lectura; Enseñanza de idiomas; Creencias; Experiencias.

Resumo

A presente pesquisa tem como discussão central os estudos direcionados às crenças e às experiências de alunos do ensino fundamental sobre o ensino de leitura em Língua Inglesa (LI). O processo de ensino-aprendizagem de LI está condicionado por uma série de fatores, dentre eles, podemos destacar a prática da leitura. A prática de leitura, de certo modo, consiste no processo de olhar para uma série de símbolos escritos e construir os significados, fazendo com que aquelas palavras possam construir significados no nosso (in)consciente. O objetivo geral é investigar as crenças e as experiências de alunos do ensino fundamental sobre o ensino de leitura em LI. Os autores que compõem os nossos pressupostos teóricos são: Barcelos (2004), Vieira-Abrahão (2006), Oliveira (2007), Paiva (2008), Miccoli (2010), Masetto (2012), Oliveira (2013), Rojo (2013), Freire (2003), Solé (2014), dentre outros. Este estudo se caracteriza como uma investigação inserida nos limites da lingüística aplicada, de natureza descritiva e interpretativa. Os sujeitos deste estudo são dois alunos do ensino fundamental de uma escola pública. Para a coleta do *corpus*, utilizamos o ‘autorrelato’ como instrumento de pesquisa. Os resultados alcançados, nesta investigação, mostram o aperfeiçoamento e o reconhecimento da leitura como ponto fundamental na sala de aula de LI. Os depoimentos dos alunos mostram uma realidade satisfatória quanto ao processo de ensino de LI, principalmente no que tange à prática de leitura. O ensino de leitura em LI pode ser uma abordagem alternativa para o contexto da escola pública.

Palavras-chave: Leitura; Ensino de Línguas; Crenças; Experiências.

Initial considerations

This article's central theme is discussions focused on the beliefs and experiences of elementary school students about teaching reading in the English language (EL). With regard to beliefs, we can observe that they present concepts that are quite old and important in understanding the main reasons for our actions. The study of beliefs about language teaching and learning has been the object of

investigation by Applied Linguistics in Brazil and abroad since 1980. As they are forms of thought constructed from our life experiences, beliefs are unstable and emergent, social and individual, with great value for scientific research in the field of human sciences. Beliefs have different types of terms that are used by researchers to indicate the intertwining between action and beliefs, for example: images, conceptions, representations, theories and culture. As it is an area with these investigative characteristics of semantic dispersion, beliefs can be considered a complex and confusing topic.

Furthermore, the field of research on experiences is linked to our daily activities, which in turn influence our beliefs and the expectations we have about these same activities. Therefore, studying aspects that contribute to the construction of human experiences can become a mechanism that instigates means, ways and forms for the teacher to be more reflective about their approaches, their interactions and the use of language in social practices, in the case of this research, the classroom context. According to Miccoli (2010a, p. 142), “the definition of experience is complex as it refers to a constellation of events nested within it”. This complex conceptualization is linked to the different aspects that teachers and students are involved in in the individual's formation process. Taking the aforementioned studies as a basis, our research focus is the experiences and beliefs of elementary school students about reading practice in the IL classroom. Experiences, which according to Miccoli (2010a, p. 29), “are a process because they have to do with relationships, dynamics and circumstances experienced in a particular environment of interactions in the classroom, are no longer an isolated or random event”. According to Barcelos (2004a, p. 18), “beliefs are a form of thought, constructions of reality, ways of seeing and perceiving the world and its phenomena”.

We can observe, from a reading perspective, that its encouragement, especially in Foreign Language (FL) classes, has been the subject of many discussions. These discussions involve, above all, their conceptions and characteristics focused on teaching. These themes have caused many questions and studies. Leffa (1999, p. 22) says that “reading is basically a process of representation. As this process involves the sense of vision, reading is, in essence, looking at one thing and seeing another.” In this way, we can understand that reading is not just limited to written material. In this case,

the author argues that reading takes place through elements of our reality. Therefore, it is necessary to activate our prior knowledge to read different things, such as: facial expression, images, written texts and the world itself. In the words of Paulo Freire (2003, p. 25): “Reading goes beyond decoding linguistic signs, it is necessary to seek understanding of what is read to understand the lived context and thus free oneself from the ideologies that prevent seeking ethical conditions to build a solidarity society”.

Analyzing the author's notes, we can observe that reading can be worked on in order to fulfill several purposes, building citizens with more critical and autonomous thoughts. Reading can be worked on in the classroom, observing not only the written text in its literal sense, as elements found on the page can often help and facilitate interpretation. Therefore, “reading is a process of interaction between the reader and the text; and in this process we try to satisfy the objectives to obtain information relevant to the objectives that guide its reading” (SOLÉ, 1998, p. 45).

In view of this discussion highlighted by Solé, we can say that reading goes far beyond the written text and teaching students to read the elements that accompany the written text can be a facilitating means for students to read as an aid in understanding the material. , because through the students' prior knowledge, a lot of separate information such as titles, images, font design, can help the student to conclude what the text is about, especially in FL classes, in which reading activities often do not pass from traditional, translation carried out with the help of a single facilitating instrument, the bilingual dictionary.

It is common for FL teachers to practice reading texts from a non-native language using only the dictionary, which is not always the best way for the student to understand the meaning of the written text. This can cause frustration in FL learners and the devaluation of other elements that accompany the written material. In this way, it makes it difficult for students to understand and causes them to become unmotivated due to the degree of difficulty that occurs in reading. Teaching in schools must be aimed at serving a new generation of students, in which students are increasingly aware of new technologies, and who tend to become unmotivated by

traditional classroom teaching. In this case, teachers can act as information mediators and pay attention to new teaching proposals.

In this way, we can observe the importance of focusing on reading exercises in FL classes, without necessarily neglecting other skills (writing, speaking and listening comprehension), using reading as a method of expanding the student's critical and cultural knowledge and improving the teaching-learning process. It may be necessary that the application of reading activities is not limited to the use of vocabulary activities and the application of grammar in the school context. It may be helpful for the teacher to understand that reading can offer much more than grammar activities.

In view of this, the teacher can, in his classes, lead students to a process of reflection on transversal themes, constructing debates about our political, economic and social reality, and, at the same time, building more critical and autonomous thoughts among students. . Furthermore, reading increases vocabulary, making the reader more familiar with the language. Taking into account the fact that English words vary in meaning depending on the context, frequent reading is an efficient method of learning the language, because it expands students' vocabulary and also prepares them for future challenges.

Conceptualizations, characteristics and contributions of beliefs and experiences applied to language teaching

By 'beliefs' we mean the action of believing in the viability of something, that is, it is the reflection of our feelings and natural emotions of thought. In other words, beliefs refer to a physical conviction related to a specific subject. The disciplines where belief studies began were anthropology, sociology, psychology, education and, mainly, philosophy. We highlight that the term 'beliefs' has been considered a complex definition (BARCELOS, 2004). Breen (1985, p.136) states that "no human institution or relationship can be adequately understood unless we consider its expectations, values and beliefs". The author's speech reaffirms the main reasons why beliefs are investigated and studied.

Beliefs became a subject of investigation abroad and, respectively, in Brazil. Studies on beliefs, in teaching and learning FL, became influential in the 1990s, with works by authors such as Leffa (1991), Almeida Filho (1993) and Barcelos (1995). It didn't stop there, research and studies on beliefs became increasingly common in teaching, including in Applied Linguistics in the 1980s. Without a doubt, the study of beliefs reached a privileged space in the readings of authors, especially in field of applied linguistics, covering their respective areas of study. The importance of knowing beliefs was highlighted by the recognition that teachers' beliefs, for example, influence teaching attitudes and methodologies, just as students' beliefs can interfere in their learning process and acquisition of English vocabulary.

Regarding the relevance of studying beliefs, Benson and Lor (1999, p. 470) state that “the value of research on learners' beliefs may lie not so much in understanding enabling or disabling attributes of beliefs, but in understanding the ways in which learners use their beliefs.” The value of studying beliefs is directly related to resources, the way and how the learner deals with the opportunity to learn other specific contexts that are different from their usual context.

According to Benson and Lor (1999, p. 464), beliefs “refer to what the learner believes to be true about these objects and processes, given a certain conception of what they are”. Regarding the author's thoughts, there is a perception that defines beliefs as being of the nature of teaching and learning and language, as there being a certain union of beliefs about languages and language in general.

We also highlight the definition of beliefs by the American philosopher Peirce (1887/1958, p.91) as “ideas that lodge themselves in people's minds as habits, customs, traditions, folk and popular ways of thinking”. In other words, the author conceptualizes beliefs as a true premise, but also as everything that is in the process of moral and cognitive integration. It is worth highlighting that beliefs are not just an intellectual formulation, but involve the entire social life, as they come from the knowledge acquired involved in the context experienced, bringing reflections and thoughts referring to a truth. It is impossible to deal with beliefs and not mention their relationship with society. To do this, we highlight Barcelos' (2006, p.18) perspective on how he understands beliefs.

A form of thought, as constructions of reality, ways of seeing and perceiving the world and its phenomena; co-constructed in our experiences and resulting from an interactive process of interpretations and (re)meaning. As such, beliefs are social (but also individual), dynamic, contextual, and paradoxical.

In this way, the author highlights the connection between beliefs and personal and social contexts, based on the assumption that beliefs refer to what we believe to be true or false. Every thought will consequently be in accordance with reality and the context in which it is inserted. This concept given by the author is important, as beliefs are directly linked to approaches in the student's learning process, relating to aspects such as: expectations, strategies, motivation, among others. Based on this perspective, we need to know the beliefs of both sides, as they can directly influence the behavior in which the entire teaching and learning process is involved.

Another aspect that we will address in this study are experiences in language teaching which, like beliefs, are quite complex and difficult to address. The Aurélio dictionary seeks to define experience, and shows that this definition is divided into four categories. In the first, the writer seeks to define experiences as the act of experiencing; experiment; experimentation. In the second, he seeks to relate experience to the practice of life, that is, his experiences acquired during his pedagogical practices in education. In the third, it seeks to define skills or expertise resulting from the continuous exercise of a profession, art or craft. In the fourth and final category, it seeks to relate attempts, trials and experiments. Miccoli (2010a, p.31-32) defines experience as

A process of a complex and organic nature that constellates within itself several other related experiences, forming a web of dynamic relationships between those who experience it, in the midst of which the experience takes place. This makes the experience a starting point for reflection, with implications for its understanding, for the transformation of its original meaning, as well as that of those who experience it.

Therefore, experiences can be considered as a complex process, which, over the years, ends up changing due to the fact that we add more experiences to compose this aspect. This entire process will build the experiences of individuals. They can be defined as the activities we perform throughout our days, which are often influenced

by the beliefs we have about these same activities. In a broad sense, we can say that experiences can be established directly by beliefs, as we only perform some activity through what we believe, and they are seen as a great source of human knowledge, which is why they are important for scientific investigation.

Experiences can play a fundamental role in the teaching and learning process of a FL. This happens because teachers and students bring, to the school context, their experiences in other environments. This means that IL classes can be transformed, moving from a traditional practice to a new reality. In the process of transforming classes, teachers and students will describe how the process of teaching and learning a foreign language occurs, and to describe this process, it is necessary to understand what experiences they have both had, being able to relate different experiences, lived in the school context or not, to understand this process (MICCOLI, 2010a, p. 18).

Some sciences sought to study, in a complex way, the definition of experiences, these are: Modern Philosophy and Cognitive Sciences. In philosophy, the concept of beliefs from experience was studied by Plato and Aristotle. Plato sought to make a distinction between experience and reason, because for him they were different things, as experience was linked to the individual's sense, something that could only be internal. Reason, on the other hand, is linked to the cognitive, that is, the consciousness of the being, which was already present after its birth. In opposition, Aristotle criticized this conceptualization of experiences inferred by Plato, as he stated that there was some type of deception due to the separation of senses and consciousness, since, for Aristotle, there is no consciousness without sense experiences.

Teaching Reading at School

Working on teaching reading is always one of the biggest and most important challenges that schools can face in terms of the IL learning process. Working on learning, from the perspective of teaching reading, is, first of all, working on learning

itself, as this is constituted from its effect on this process. In this aspect, we can observe that “[...] without the expected learning, teaching did not fulfill its purpose of making people learn” (BOTH, 2005, p. 55), because “teaching does not exist without learning and vice versa [...]” (FREIRE, 1996, p. 12).

Addressing discussions and studies focused on learning, from the perspective of teaching reading, is increasingly important and indispensable, as we can verify that the results presented by reading approaches on performance in this practice are indispensable for training and, consequently, learning of students inserted in the context of basic education. However, we can see that the results for this discussion show us that students present some difficulties and challenges to this teaching approach, as they present a certain fragility with regard to the skills and abilities that they need to develop throughout their training in basic education (BRITO; SANTOS, 2021).

Due to several situations that have occurred in recent years, such as the spread of false information and the lack of verification of this information, it has been observed that the media are used to directly influence important decisions by society. As a result, educational institutions have been working and intensifying, through different methodologies, to meet current demands. Schools and teachers are increasingly instructed to address teaching and learning reading in their methodologies to form readers capable of dealing with these needs. This work proposes a study focused on discussions about teaching reading from different perspectives. For example, in the perspective linked to the evidence presented in research already carried out in the context of challenges and difficulties that teachers face in training readers in the critical aspect. All of this, with the aim of expanding debates, in an attempt to find ways towards overcoming the weaknesses encountered so far.

Given the above, we agree with some studies that point to the great relevance and/or importance of approaches and studies of beliefs and experiences as elements that are directly linked to the actions of teachers in the classroom (BARCELOS, 2006; BOMFIM; CONCEIÇÃO, 2009) and, consequently, these beliefs and experiences are

directly linked to the impact on the relevance of student learning, as teaching and learning are results of what we believe and think. Therefore, when we approach the different conceptions of reading in school institutions, we can perceive and learn about the beliefs and experiences in different approaches to reading conceived in the classroom over the years.

Therefore, we observe that in the historical context, reading was and is seen, especially in the school context, through different conceptions, mainly due to the fact that there are different ways of understanding this area of knowledge. These thoughts are linked, as they are generally linked to the beliefs that teachers and the institution have about the process of teaching, for whom and why to teach.

For the reading process to be expanded, the subject needs to be able to establish relationships between their prior knowledge and the text, reflecting on the information transmitted. A critical reader is able to attribute value to linked information, thus building their position. (OLIVEIRA, 2015, p. 148)

Before we discuss the main discussions and studies on the reading perspective, it is important to understand the main definitions regarding this aspect of study. So what is reading? According to research by Saito (2018), when addressing the importance of the reading process, emphasizing that this methodology results from some indispensable processes, which is linked to three stages: the first stage addresses the reading process as something simple, mainly due to what is reproduced after the text has been read, highlighting that this stage brings a superficial reading, without more in-depth analysis of what the author of the text says or meant; the second stage brings reading comprehension into a more complex scope, seeking to extract implicit information and meanings from the text, seeking to understand what is beyond the written text and worrying about understanding the message that the text or author conveys; the third and final stage corresponds to reading in a more critical aspect, seeking to increase the ability to understand what is between the lines of the text, to judge, evaluate and consciously apply what is read.

After bringing discussions about the three stages of reading, we will now discuss the three understandings about reading that are extracted from these stages, they are: reproducing information; extract information and implicit meanings from

texts as a way of understanding them; confront knowledge, become aware of the world and act critically in society. Silva (2009) also brings similar discussions and makes reference to these stages, describing them as types of reading and classifying them as mechanical reading, world reading and critical reading.

It is important that these definitions do not cause any type of confusion to those who are studying reading, as care is needed to differentiate them and emphasize which aspect of reading the school is expected to help students develop to correspond to contemporary social demands. In this section, we explain the type of reading required by contemporary society and which is officially oriented towards Brazilian schools.

Methodological Aspects

This topic brings a discussion regarding the methodology adopted throughout this research, outlining and addressing the main constituent aspects of this work. Based on the influences on the practice of reading in the teaching and learning process of IL in the school context, and, specifically, in relation to the beliefs and experiences of students, it is of notable importance to carry out qualitative research of a descriptive and interpretivist so that the theory can be deepened. According to this theoretical basis, there is a need to verify students' beliefs and experiences regarding the practice of reading in IL classes. Minayo (2004, p. 21) explains a little about qualitative research and states that

Qualitative research answers very particular questions. It is concerned, in the social sciences, with a level of reality that cannot be quantified. In other words, it works with the universe of meanings, motives, aspirations, beliefs, values and attitudes, which corresponds to a deeper space of relationships, processes and phenomena that cannot be reduced to the operationalization of variables.

In the aforementioned passage, the author seeks to show how qualitative research is structured, showing that it studies the lines between the discourses, and not the number of subjects researched. In this case, we seek to study the meanings of each self-report, showing how reasons, beliefs and experiences can influence the discourse.

The research was carried out in a basic/public elementary school in a city in the upper west of the state of Rio Grande do Norte. The institution covers levels I and II of elementary education, more specifically, from the 1st to the 9th year. The school has an excellent physical structure, with 8 large classrooms, a library, a computer room, an auditorium, a room for the school management, a teachers' room, two rooms for school coordination, a room for making copies of activities, four bathrooms for students (two for students from 1st to 5th grade and two for students from 6th to 9th grade), a cafeteria and a large courtyard.

The institution operates in the morning and afternoon. In the morning shift, regular education is taught (1st to 9th grade) and, in the afternoon, it is intended for school reinforcement, proposed to students who have some deficit in regular education, and EJA (Youth and Adult Education) teaching. With regard to technological equipment, the school has computers, datashow and internet, making teachers' practice and students' learning more effective.

In characterizing the corpus of this research, we investigated two (2) students from elementary school II, more specifically from the 9th year, from the basic/public education network. The objective was to relate and investigate how students' beliefs and experiences about teaching reading are established in the IL educational context. We selected 2 students, who will be described as A1 (Student 1) and A2 (Student 2), from the 9th year class, as we believe that they would be better able to answer our questions and, also, so that we can understand how it is established this practice in the reality of this class.

In research on beliefs and experiences, we recognize that the data collection instrument is extremely important, as it is through it that the participant can describe the context in which they are inserted, being able to evaluate their actions and procedures during their reading practices. . In turn, the collection procedure for this research consists of applying a 'self-report'. This method consists of a single question, or survey, in which respondents read, interpret the question and select an answer for themselves, without interference from the researcher.

The analysis of this research was divided into three categories and two subcategories. In the first category, the analysis was established based on students' experiences of teaching reading in IL practice. As subcategories, we will have experiences on teaching reading. Therefore, only those parts that matched the students' experiences were selected and analyzed. In the second category, we will seek to analyze students' beliefs about teaching reading. As subcategories, we will analyze beliefs about teaching reading. As in the first category, we select and analyze only the parts that match the beliefs. Finally, we have the implications of beliefs and experiences for language teaching. In this category, we will analyze how beliefs and experiences can influence the IL learning process.

Results of Reaserch

After a great deal of organization, elaboration and application of self-reports to students, and, subsequently, the construction of analysis categories, we sought to interpret this material by discussing its interrelationships and the relationship with the theories addressed throughout this study. This category and subcategory show an analysis of self-reports focused on describing and interpreting students' experiences in relation to reading practice in the context of the IL classroom. Next, we will see some reports about students' experiences in relation to reading practice in language teaching.

A1 and A2 - The experiences I have in terms of reading practice are **the reading project**, where we read chapters of works in LI. This project **is very interesting and relevant to our learning**.

According to A1's statement, experiences focused on reading practices are directly related to the reading project. The student also highlights that this project contributes positively to his training. The second category and its subcategory show an analysis of self-reports focusing on the description and interpretation of students' beliefs regarding teaching reading in IL classroom approaches. The students' statements point to teaching reading as a way of complementing the content taught

in the classroom and a way of getting closer to the language taught. Next, we will see some reports about students' beliefs regarding the use of reading practice in language teaching.

A1 - I believe that **reading** allows us to get closer to the **language studied** and also makes us know more words, **developing our learning**.

A2 - Reading **is an excellent study opportunity to reinforce writing and expand our vocabulary in different contexts**. As a consequence, reading books/texts in English will bring you closer to the language studied.

Given this, A1 and A2 are very similar in their statements, pointing to reading practice as a way of getting closer to the language covered and improving their knowledge. Therefore, we consider their self-reports to be noteworthy, mainly due to the positive points about the practice of reading, showing that reading brings a proximity to the language studied. Regarding this practice, students say it is a positive approach and tends to develop their knowledge.

In the third category, which is data analysis, we can highlight that beliefs and experiences about teaching reading and learning IL have some implications for the teaching and learning process of students. Silva (2005, p. 24) states that “the first implication refers to the process of allowing/encouraging future teachers to become aware of their own beliefs, and beliefs in general, those existing even in Literature of Applied Linguistics”.

The first implication of the beliefs focused on the teaching and learning of IL, in our view, has the objective of helping in the intellectual formation of students, where they will begin to develop their criticality in the world around them through reading. Students will become more reflective, that is, they will reflect on their actions performed in the context of learning in the classroom.

The first implication of the beliefs focused on the teaching and learning of IL, in our view, has the objective of helping in the intellectual formation of students, where they will begin to develop their criticality in the world around them through reading. Students will become more reflective, that is, they will reflect on their actions performed in the context of learning in the classroom. Regarding the implications of

beliefs and experiences, discussed previously, students, as already mentioned, also have beliefs that will imply and are decisive in the process of learning a foreign language, because as we know, beliefs act directly in the approach to process of acquiring knowledge, then this aspect will directly influence your actions in the classroom. Therefore, beliefs and experiences are decisive in the teaching and learning process. Then, the need arises for the student, together with the teachers, to know their beliefs and experiences so that they are able to avoid any type of conflict. By knowing their beliefs and experiences, students will be guided in their actions in the classroom, thus bringing success in their training and in learning IL.

Final considerations

The focus of carrying out this research is based on the relevance that reading practices have for teaching, based on the learning practices of elementary school students. Thus, students' beliefs and experiences about teaching reading can guide us regarding the IL learning process, given that the practice is conditioned by what we think and what we experience in everyday life. The research had the general objective of investigating the beliefs and experiences of elementary school students about teaching reading linked to digital technologies.

Therefore, we understand that the experiences and beliefs about teaching reading linked to the use of digital technologies show that students' self-reports present favorable and efficient aspects regarding the efficiency in conducting English language teaching. Through these self-reports, we can imagine how students have gained interest and motivation in the learning process. This aspect is very important, since we understand that this practice is extremely important for the development of learning.

Therefore, in this learning process, teachers need to awaken students' interest and motivation, given that they are tired of teaching focused only on the textbook. We can also highlight that the results achieved in this investigation are that teachers seek, in different ways and methodologies, to use digital technologies linked to

teaching reading within the school context. Consequently, due recognition of this approach as important elements for the development of classroom activities is observed. The benefits brought by the inclusion of this practice in the students' English language teaching-learning process are clear.

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